

"The founder of an independent state, a great statesman and politician"

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Annotation: In this article, the founder of the independent state of Uzbekistan, a great statesman and political figure, an honored son of the Uzbek people, the First President of our country, Islam Abdugyanovich Karimov, freed our country from the dependence of the autocratic system and restored our country, which was on the brink of destruction, a brilliant political It has been widely reported that he left an indelible mark in history by showing selflessness in the way of the welfare of the people and the development of the country with his noble human qualities. Islam Abduganiyevich Karimov left an indelible mark in the centuries-old history of our country with his brilliant political activity and noble human qualities. He was recognized as a great person and figure who received great respect and prestige not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the world.

Key words: Islam Abdugyanovich Karimov, January 30, 1938, "mechanical engineer", 21st school, "Toshselmash", candidacy on the topic "The network structure of the industry of the Uzbek SSR and the main directions of its improvement" dissertation work, "macroeconomics", "Red Flag of Labor" (1981), "Friendship of Nations" (1988), "Unity", "Erk", independence, August 31, 1991, January 9, 2000, December 23, 2007, March 29, 2015, Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan (1994), "High Spirituality - Invincible Power" (2008), September 2, 2016

The founder of the independent state of Uzbekistan, a great statesman and political figure, a great and honorable son of the Uzbek people, the First President of our country, Islam Abduganiyevich Karimov, freed our country from the dependence of the authoritarian regime and restored our country, which was on the verge of destruction. Our great leader turned Uzbekistan into a modern democratic state developing rapidly and steadily in a historically short period of time, despite severe difficulties and trials in a very unstable and dangerous situation. Islam Abduganiyevich Karimov left an indelible mark in the centuries-old history of our country with his

brilliant political activity and noble human qualities. He was recognized as a great person and figure who received great respect and prestige not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the world.

Islam Abduganiyevich Karimov was born on January 30, 1938 in the city of Samarkand in the family of an ordinary servant. In his family, daily hard work was the only way to earn money for living. His childhood coincided with the war and post-war years. He and all his relatives experienced hardships and poverty without knowing the true value of bread. Like thousands of our compatriots, they shared their home and bread with people who were evacuated to Uzbekistan during the Second World War.

In 1945, Islam Karimov entered the 21st school named after A.S. Pushkin in Samarkand and graduated with a gold medal. During his school years, he read a lot of literature, especially literature on history. She liked science, was interested in chess, modeling and table tennis. In 1955, Islam Abdughanievich entered the Polytechnic Institute of Central Asia. In 1960, after graduating from it and receiving a diploma in "engineer-mechanic" specialty, he started working at the "Toshselmash" plant and in a short period managed to work in the positions of foreman's assistant, foreman and technologist. This factory produced various types of agricultural machinery, including cotton picking machines. They eased the labor of the farmers of Uzbekistan and other republics, and were also exported to other countries. It was important for Islam Abduganiyevich to feel all this in his body, to gain experience in production, to see the "complex" and "positive" aspects of factory life. Due to his ambition, knowledge and organizational qualities, in 1961 he was appointed to the position of an engineer in one of the largest enterprises of the military-industrial complex of the former Soviet Union - the Tashkent Aviation Plant. He worked here until 1966 and rose to the position of leading engineer-designer. Fate did not smile at him.

He had to overcome a number of difficulties and obstacles. This would strengthen his character and make him stronger. He walked the path of life, first of all, relying on his strength and knowledge. He relied on his strength and knowledge during his school years, at the institute, during his work in production, and when he received economic education and defended his dissertation. He received education without separating from production. In this way, in 1967, he graduated from the evening department of the Tashkent Institute of National Economy. In 1973, he defended his candidate's thesis at the Tashkent Institute of National Economy on the topic "Network structure of the

industry of the Uzbek SSR and the main directions of its improvement". In 1975, he studied modern methods of management and organization of production and planning using economic-mathematical methods and computing techniques at the prestigious Institute of Public Economy Management in Moscow. In 1994, he was awarded the degree of Doctor of Economic Sciences, was awarded the scientific title of professor in the field of "macroeconomics". He was elected a full member of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, majoring in "economy". Since 1966, Islam Abdugyanevich joined the State Planning Committee of Uzbekistan from the position of chief specialist of the science department to the position of first deputy chairman of the State Planning Committee. earned a reputation as a gifted economist with unique thinking. In 1983 he became the Minister of Finance, in 1986 he became the Deputy Chairman of the Council of Ministers - the Chairman of the State Planning Committee of Uzbekistan.

Economist, theoretician and practitioner Islam Karimov realized that the administrative-command system of economic management is completely wrong. Having worked through the ranks of the State Planning Committee and the Ministry of Finance, which formed the plans for the financial and economic development of the republic, having an analytical mind, he felt from the inside the problems that had arisen, which no one knew about. In 1986, Islam Abduganiyevich, who was the chairman of the State Planning Committee of the UZSSR, after studying the situation in depth, realized that the republic was facing an economic disaster. Understanding the situation and wanting to change it for the better, he prepared a reference for the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan "On the problems and prospects of the development of the economy of Uzbekistan". He hoped that serious and specific measures would be taken. But the situation caused the anger of the leadership to such an extent that it was not possible for him to stay in Tashkent from now on. The desire to get rid of the "undesirable" I.A. Karimov was so strong that due to this, the party violated the established order of appointment to the post of the first secretary of the regional party committee. Thus, he was appointed in absentia as the first secretary of the party committee of Kashkadarya region at the meeting of the Political Bureau. In practice, it was his "exile" away from the center.

Islam Abduganiyevich was sent to a very difficult region. The socio-economic situation in the whole of Uzbekistan was not easy, and in the Kashkadarya region, the situation was much more complicated, because the previous leadership of the region

had lost its reputation in the eyes of the people, and there was no trust in the party leaders. Perhaps Islam Abduganievich's appointment to Kashkadarya was necessary to break him, but on the contrary, it turned his fate around. He worked in Kashkadarya for almost three years. His main goal was to win the people's trust, change their attitude towards the authorities, and improve the situation in the region. And he did it. Almost 300 km of roads, markets, social and cultural facilities were built. Until now, people in the region fondly remember the days when Islam Abduganiyevich Karimov worked.

No matter what position Islam Karimov held, he remained, first of all, a citizen of his country, he wanted his people to live happily and prosperously. The people also felt the positive changes in their lives, and not only looked at him with great confidence, but also became true supporters of their leader. In those years, his services to the Motherland were awarded with the "Red Flag of Labor" (1981) and "Friendship of Peoples" (1988) orders.

On August 31, 1991, at the sixth extraordinary session of the Supreme Soviet of the Uzbek SSR of the 12th convocation, I.A. Karimov announced the state independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan. On the same day, he signed the Law "On the Basics of State Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan". As early as August 1990, Islam Karimov began to reorganize the Communist Party, supported the wise opinion of our people that "do not destroy the old one before building a new one", and tried to fundamentally change its ideology and policy. The ruling party with huge reserves of people and administration was transformed into a people's democratic party with a completely new ideology and policy. At the moment when the reputation of the Communist Party fell, alternative parties and movements appeared, such as Birlik and Erk parties, which declared themselves as opponents. Despite the complexity of the internal political situation in the country, Islam Karimov emphasized diversity of opinions and democratic demonstrated commitment to values and decided to take a bold step - hold elections on the basis of multi-partyism and alternatives.

The election was held on December 29, 1991 by secret ballot on the basis of universal, equal and direct suffrage. Islam Abduganiyevich Karimov was elected to this high position with an absolute majority. 86% of voters voted for him. Simultaneously with the presidential election, a referendum on the independence of Uzbekistan was held. Almost all citizens who came to vote expressed their opinion for an independent sovereign Uzbekistan.

With his victory in the election, Islam Karimov confirmed the legitimacy of his policy, which was supported by the entire nation. This confirmation of the legitimacy of his powers in the position of the President, undoubtedly, further strengthened Islam Karimov's confidence in the correctness of the work he is doing to strengthen independence and implement long-awaited political and economic reforms. In a historically short period of time, the main law - the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan - was developed and adopted in our country, which clearly defined the main principles of the state and society. In order to use his constitutional experience in working on the Basic Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Abdugyanevich directly participated in the work on it, and used the constitutions of countries such as the USA, GFR, Japan, Canada, France, Portugal, Italy, Sweden, Turkey, Spain, India, Pakistan, Egypt. studied in detail.

Islam Abdug'aniyevich, while leading the commission on the development of the Basic Law, saw the future of Uzbekistan as a great country based on the principles of humanitarianism and ensuring the rights and freedoms of citizens, regardless of nationality, religion, social status and political beliefs. he asked.

Within three months, the draft Constitution passed public discussion, more than 6,000 proposals were submitted and considered by the commission. On December 8, 1992, the Supreme Council of Uzbekistan adopted this historical document. The new Constitution binds citizens and the state through rights and obligations. In this sense, the document embodies all the principles of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, that is, the rule of inviolability of life, person and human freedom. I.A. Karimov was elected President of the Republic of Uzbekistan several times by direct, general, secret voting on the basis of alternative, and every time he received an absolute majority of voters. This was observed on January 9, 2000, December 23, 2007, and March 29, 2015.

At present, there are four political parties operating in our country, which have their own action programs and electorates and participate in elections at all levels, including the election of the President of the country, the Oliy Majlis and deputies of local Councils. These are the People's Democratic Party of Uzbekistan, the Democratic Party of Uzbekistan "National Revival", the Movement of Entrepreneurs and Businessmen - the Liberal-Democratic Party of Uzbekistan, the Social-Democratic

Party of Uzbekistan "Adolat". In addition, the environmental movement of Uzbekistan is actively working in our country.

It is impossible to imagine any country without national symbols such as the flag and coat of arms. And here it is worth noting that the author of these important symbols of independent Uzbekistan is Islam Abduganiyevich Karimov. He is also the author of the creation of awards such as "Independence", "Amir Temur", "For meritorious services". On March 2, 1992, Uzbekistan was admitted to the United Nations as a full subject of international law. This marked a qualitatively new stage in the development of our republic, as well as an opportunity for active international economic, scientific-technical and cultural cooperation. 133 countries have established diplomatic relations with Uzbekistan as a subject of international relations.

Uzbekistan is a member of more than 100 international organizations, actively participating in the work of prestigious international organizations such as the United Nations, the Organization of Islamic Cooperation, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe, the Commonwealth of Independent States, regional and made a significant contribution to solving many issues of global development.

Islam Karimov has three children and six grandchildren, communication with them brought him great joy. His wife - Tatyana Akbarovna was his true friend, assistant, like-minded person, happily married to Islam Abduganievich for 47 years and shared all the hardships of life with him. Karimov was elected to the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan (1994), as well as an honorary doctor of science, professor and academician of more than ten foreign universities and academies for his great contribution to the development of economy, science, and education. Islam Karimov:

1. "Uzbekistan's own path of independence and development" (1992),
2. "Do not destroy the old one without building a new one" (1993),
3. "Uzbekistan is a unique way of transition to market relations" (1993),
4. "Let a free and prosperous Motherland remain from us" (1994),
5. "Independence and Spirituality" (1994),
6. "The motherland is as sacred as a place of worship" (1995),
7. "Uzbekistan on the threshold of the 21st century: threats to security, conditions of stability and guarantees of development" (1997),
8. "The dream of a perfect generation" (1998),

9. "From a strong state to a strong society" (1998),
10. "There is no future without historical memory" (1998),
11. "Allah is in our heart, in our heart" (1999),
12. "A free and prosperous homeland, a free and prosperous life is our ultimate goal" (2000),
13. "We must fight for security and peace" (2001),
14. "The main directions of further deepening of democratic changes and formation of the foundations of civil society in Uzbekistan" (2002)
15. "High Spirituality - Invincible Power" (2008)
16. "Uzbekistan: national independence, economy, political ideology"
17. "From the path of creativity"
18. "New way of thinking and working - state demand"
19. "Towards security and sustainable development"
20. "We build our future with our own hands"
21. "Each of us is responsible for the development of the country"
22. "The path we have chosen is the path of democratic development and cooperation with the enlightened world"
23. "Our peace and security depend on our strength, unity and will"
24. "The Uzbek people will never be dependent on anyone"
25. "Man, his rights and freedoms are the highest value"
26. "Liberating our society, deepening reforms, raising our morale and raising the standard of living of our people is the criterion and goal of all our work"
27. "Towards modernization of the country and sustainable development of our economy"
28. "Ensuring gradual and stable development of our country is our highest goal"
29. "Towards overcoming the consequences of the world crisis, modernizing our country and rising to the level of developed countries"
30. "The deepening of democratic reforms and the formation of a civil society are the main criteria for the development of our country"Dad:
31. "Our way is to deepen democratic reforms and consistently continue modernization processes"
32. "On the way to resolutely continue the improvement and modernization of our country"

33. "Uzbekistan's achievements and milestones are a confirmation of the path of reforms we have chosen"

34. "It is our most urgent task today to raise our started reforms to a new level without limiting ourselves to the achieved goals"

35. "Serving for the happiness, fortune and future of our motherland is the highest happiness"

36. "A nation that has breathed its fill of the air of freedom will never turn back from its path."

37. He is the author of the works "The people of Kashkadarya who have overcome the trials of life are capable of achieving any high level".

State awards of Islam Abduganiyevich Karimov, the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

1. The title of "Hero of Uzbekistan".
2. "Golden Star" medal
3. Order of "Independence".
4. "Amir Temur" order
5. Order of the Red Banner of Labor
6. Order of "Friendship of Peoples".
7. "For peace and harmony among peoples" medal and diploma
8. Grand "Mogunxva 2" order
9. "Avicenna" gold medal
10. "Golden Iran" ("Golden Eagle") Order
11. Order of Prince Daniil, I degree
12. Order of "Yaroslav Mudriy" 1st degree
13. Gold Order "Five Continents Sign".
14. "International Leader" award for his outstanding contribution to the fight against terrorism
15. "Cisneros" medal and honorary diploma
16. Order of Vytautas the Great
17. "Golden Key" of the city of Budapest
18. Order "For Civil Services".
19. The Golden Key of Madrid
20. Golden Order of "Andrei Pervozvanny".

21. Order "For services" I degree
22. "Zolotoye runo" order
23. Order "Stara Planina".
24. Gold Order "Saint Nicholas of Karamatgoy".
25. "Borobodur" gold medal
26. "Aristotle" gold medal
27. "Great Silk Road" gold medal
28. Honorary title of "Honorable Year of Greenery".
29. Order of "Three Stars".
30. "For contribution to strengthening friendship" award
31. Honorary badge "For services to the University".
32. II degree "Order of the Republic of Serbia"
33. Order "Cross of Recognition".
34. Order of "Courage".
35. International award named after Mahtumkuli
36. Jubilee medal "70th anniversary of victory over fascism in World War II".
37. Medal of the International Olympic Committee "For outstanding contribution to the development of sports and the Olympic movement"
38. Award of the Olympic Council of Asia for his great contribution to the development of football in Uzbekistan and Asia
39. Order "For services".
40. Crystal globe

Islam Abduganiyevich Karimov, the founder of our independent state, died on September 2, 2016 at 20:55 in Tashkent due to a stroke.

Sincere love and deep respect for the first President was especially strongly manifested during the days of mourning. At that time, all our people followed our First President with tears to his last destination. About 60 years ago, a young talented boy who graduated from school with a gold medal was taken away from this city by fate, and now he returned to his native land to his final destination as the independent President of Uzbekistan.

The death of Islam Abduganiyevich was a very heavy and irreparable loss for all residents of our republic. Islam Abduganiyevich wanted to be buried in the land of his mother Samarkand. And his will was fulfilled. On September 3, 2016, the First

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President of Uzbekistan was buried in the ancient Hazrat Hizr Mosque of his small homeland - the city of Samarkand.

While working on his speech dedicated to the 25th anniversary of the independence of Uzbekistan, Islam Abduganiyevich Karimov wanted to end his speech with the following words. He did not have time to say these words. Now these words are a testament to our people:

"May the Creator help us in all our good deeds and help us!"

May our country be peaceful, our sky clear, and our people safe!

May our independence be forever!"

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4. Wikipedia.org;
5. "High spirituality - invincible power" (2008);
6. "Uzbekistan: national independence, economy, political ideology";
7. "Through creativity";
8. "Each of us is responsible for the development of the country";
9. "The path we have chosen is the path of democratic development and cooperation with the enlightened world";
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